

Morality, an error from the Trickster god.

to err is to exist, to perceive error is to think, to knowingly err is human.

Abstract

I propose a formal representation of morality as prediction error, in the context and notation of Active Inference, a framework that understands self-organizing and sentient systems as statistical models of their environment. Explicating (vocally declaring) behavior that deviated from expectations and labeling offenders as deviants cultivates an inference of free will, essentially as (existential) model selection. This involves the inference of a higher superordinate contextual prediction level, or reference frame, where perceived divergences from the prior generative model constitutes the moral agency to select a narrower or broader existential model. The posterior belief of agents as capable of modeling their own beliefs marks the transitional gateway to abstraction, propositional content, i.e. deviants are symbolic labels and the cultural niche becomes a symbolic identity. This draw on demonstration that moral beliefs are core to our linguistic and social systems, and finally it involves a plausible phylogentic route that proposes our cultural niche is founded on our use of accent bias to expand our social unit, frame of reference, or markov blanket.

Introduction

Morality is complex. Perhaps an unlikely candidate to start a topic about linguistics, economics, sociology, or humanity's origins? Zhuangzi, Socrates, Kant, Siddhartha and likely our ancestors since their time in the Pleistocene have spent many a day trying to explain morality. However what if we can take a view of morality simply (but not too simply) as a particular type of failed expectation?

If you found yourself walking down the street and saw a man walk up to a lady, take her hat, don it himself, and walk away. You would be appalled. Not because you had explicitly thought, before that observation, that people should only wear their own hats, but nonetheless you might find yourself shouting something along the lines of "hey, you can't take someone's hat fool how dare you!" Declaring what seems like an obvious fact to two strangers, and along with the other passersby, all of whom you find in

agreement as they start to join your admonishment against this hat caper. The man, now seeming confused, takes the cat off his head, sheepishly returns it to the lady and walks away.

$$Objective_{Human} \approx Min(\epsilon^{obj})$$

Representing humanity as a function that tries to minimize error explicitly.

The point is that while the *explicit prohibition* against hat theft is separate from a prediction of the stock market, if we understand our seemingly unique symbolic social behavior and mind as a *prediction error signal*, analogous to those that our nervous system continually generates, e.g. see (Clark 2016), then it may represent a sort of harnessing of this fundamental life and existential process. This is in the tradition of Active Inference, which understands error minimization as a fundamental process to all forms of life and offers a detailed rigorous and formal ontology around this view. I believe we can view our innate moral impulses and our immutable passion for norm abidance as intimately connected to our symbolic consciousness. The inter-subjective and above ground triangulation of perspective involved in morality underwrites the general part-whole (feature-gestalt) cognitive oscillation necessary for our abstract thought and interpretation.

$$P(\theta_{SymSelf}^A | \epsilon^{obj}) = \tilde{g}^{obj}(\tilde{g}^{n+i}(\theta_{[c,d]}))$$

Intuitively, the above proposes humanity's prior belief in, or ability to treat norms as morally objective fosters the belief in a symbolic self (ϵ) represents morality as the failed expectations, or prediction error, of the symbolic identity humanity inhabits. Normally the belief (θ) would be conditioned on the evidence as y , here I swap an objectified error term to indicate the explication, objectiveness, or thingness rather than an implication of a failed prediction. This represents morality that follows an inferred descent from an objective layer. More formally, unpacked below.

Morality is not something we are generally taught explicitly, whether as infants or, as the example show, as adults. We naturally form certain

expectations about your caretakers and con-specifics that, we can reasonably interpret with a moral dimension, e.g. showing a preference for prosocial vs antisocial puppets, see (Bloom 2013). Moreover we innately display extensive altruistic behavior (Barragan, Brooks, and Meltzoff 2020), that suggests our preferences and priorities extend beyond our own skin and even our caretakers and kin.

This supports the idea of moral intuitions, see (Weaver, Reynolds, and Brown 2014), however these intuitions are also adjacent to our impulse to subsequently *declare* our beliefs, e.g. see the research on gossiping (Dunbar 2004), not to mention the formal moral theorizing of the Plato and Zhaungzi types. The question is what is the relationships between the psychologically innate moral beliefs, and those beliefs we verbalize explicitly.

To bridge this gap I propose a high level representation of morality that includes an iterative process of implicit expectations followed by explicated errors. This answers an important question about morality but also suggests that this bridge is fundamental to our general engagement with propositional, i.e. abstract content. By explicating the error we took hold of the predictive modeling process that is understood in Active Inference frameworks as at the heart of existence.

Active Inference, along with the Free Energy Principle (FEP), took the insight that emerged in neuroscience, that our brain is a prediction machine seeking to make and update guesses about the outside world, and scaled that to all forms of life. Noting that cells can be understood mathematically as models of their environment, and that our biology can be broadly modularized in similar formalisms as, say, visual perception processing.

More broadly, against the backdrop of the non-diminishing uncertainty complex and living systems emerge as model of their environment, critical to the ability to minimize uncertainty is the use of prediction errors. Not only do they initiate the central feedback loop that allows for perception and action, living systems can be viewed as particularly erroneous, or statistically

biased towards those elements (states) that constitute its own existence. Homeostatic and allostatic set points in-group bias, or even what we would call the *selfish* behavior of a knave (or a toddler) all underscore an essential motive of sentient and autopoietic behavior to place the thumb of the scale in favor of one's own existence.

$$F[Q_v, \epsilon^{obj}] \geq D_{KL} Q_v(x_v) || P(x_A | \epsilon^{obj}, M_A) - \ln(P(\epsilon^{obj} | M_A))$$

This attempts to (parsimoniously) capture the departure from the nonsymbolic to the symbolic, or virtual world. Like all cognitive systems our capacity to form approximate, selfishly biased environmental niche models underwrites our existence. The variables D_{KL} represents an agent's attempt to mathematically depict its world, where Q and F represents probabilistic approximations of the true process that generates the statistical data that, according to Active Inference, agents are trying to be a model of. I represent a 'virtual' posterior $Q(x)$ associated with an explicated error that departs from the 'actual' (A) model of the presymbolic world.

Morality represents the expectation of a broader in-group. The surprise invoked by hat theft and other defiant actions do not simply trigger an emotional response from the onlookers, it prompts them to *label* the offender. Brandishing this anonymous compatriot with a new identity that is directly connected to their beliefs, this identity can be seen as an integrated and hierarchical generative model. Analogous to inferring that another agent possesses subjective, mental states underwrites the self-awareness of our own conscious experience, by observing that others can deviate from objective expectations they effectively possess a freedom that, in this simple schematic, involves a narrow allegiance, or faith in the individual rather than the shared self or community.

Humanity's Trick: Toggling Models

I am attempting here to formalize my theoretical paper in *Frontiers*, *The Myth of Objectivity and the Origin of Symbols* (Rahman 2023), where I

argue, using the Free Energy Principle and Active Inference against more traditional single equilibrium and reductive frameworks used across social and behavioral sciences, that our symbolic capacity is tied to our shared belief in moral objectivity. This involved transcending individual, subjective perspective, establishing a viewpoint for our cultural niche, in order to minimize a specific type of uncertainty.

This uncertainty arises in anonymous societies of, complex agents such as primates, many of who possess critical features of morality despite a lack of the symbolic dimension:

[T]hough full-blown human morality is unique to humans, several of its key elements are not. [...] a review of evidence from non-human primates regarding prosocial concern, conformity, and the potential presence of universal, biologically anchored and arbitrary cultural norms shows that these elements of morality are not distributed evenly across primate species. [...] [M]any if not all of the elements of morality found in non-human primates are only evident in individualistic or dyadic contexts, but not as third-party reactions by truly uninvolved bystanders [...] Primate proactive prosociality has mostly been studied from the dyadic perspective. However, in humans, it also encompasses the third-party context (Burkart 2018).

One way to understand Burkart and colleagues distinction between dyadic normative behavior and the requirement that human morality take into account third-party, neutral perspectives is to consider that human, while similarly in many ways to other primates include anonymous in-group members. In this social context necessary to evaluate social behavior from a shared perspective.

One possible route I suggest is that our use of Shibboleth, or accent bias, served as a precursor to symbolic social organization by allowing us to cohabit with conspecifics with whom we were not intimate, fostering the cognitive capacity for and motivating the drive to minimize uncertainty using

labels (i.e. social types). This led to the *belief* that agents possess their own capacity to *believe*, i.e. a recursion analogous to the recognition and self-recognition [fundamental to consciousness](#), in a way that amounts to free will. Thus creating our ability to abstract the modeling process at the heart of Active Inference.

One important thread that runs through the framework is prediction error, that gives way not just to the establishment of expectations and the feedback loop of evidence gained through perceiving sense data and producing it through action, but the notion that the individual itself *is an error*, in the sense that an agent is an otherwise accurate model of its environment, but one that is statically biased towards its own identity (optimism bias), and that cognitive systems are distinct from non cognitive systems by possessing approximate prior beliefs of their generative process (niche). The act of synthesizing a perspective constitutes an explication of a fundamental feature of living systems that we can view, in accordance with Active Inference, as the implicit environmental-modeling process of the Self. By Stepping *up and out* of our own vantage point and intuiting an above-the-fray viewpoint, we create a higher order inference (i.e. an inference of an inference).

This concurs with recent rework that looks at [transcendental experiences](#), where people report higher order cognitive states, my claim is that an error signal envisaged from a synthesized superordinate level gave rise to those higher states and thus we can understand our symbolic capacity as analogous to the hierarchical connections of, for example, the nervous system. It also fits within Lars Sandved-Smith and colleagues' [computational model of meta-awareness](#), as a higher order hierarchical states (Sandved-Smith et al. 2021). This also aligns with John Vervaeke's description of our symbolic capacity as involving a [transjective](#) (*involving but superseding both objective and subjective*).

the trickster

The neural mechanisms that underlie humanity's cognitive capacity for symbolic abstraction are of course complex and can likely be modeled in a number of ways, the goal I'd like to embark on is to align with Active Inference and the broader framework it fits into, the FEP, and an important principle of parsimony, i.e. as simple as possible but no simpler than that (Friston et al. 2022). It has been described as nearly [tautological](#) by its most noteworthy proponents and a [trick by its detractors](#), claiming that its explanatory power rely on its invocation of the Markov blanket, the states which distinguish a system from its environment and underwrite the application of a host of mathematical analysis, from fields ranging from control theory, information, theory, economics, thermodynamics, etc. If it is a trick, it is one humanity used in its capacity to produce symbols.

The FEP applies the insight that cognition is essentially a predictive modeling machine as an existential ontology, to all things, whether living or physical. Critical here is the meta element, that states for things to exist as distinct objects in a world of increasing uncertainty they must *be* (i.e. embody) a parsimonious model of their environment, capturing the economic or budgetary notion of Darwinian evolution, that nature imposes a cost for both complex solutions to environmental challenges as well as insufficiently predictive or inaccurate solutions and requires a trade off, yet it frames this intuition into an operable drive to find an optimal balance between the two poles with an appropriate *model fit*.

This enables agents to identify and inhabit a set of states that underwrite their observable biological phenomena, adjusting in real time to variations in the environment and adapting to novel challenges, in other words, it is an essential process within natural selection and allows things to exist despite, as assured by the second law of thermodynamics, the tendency for uncertainty to increase. How then does humanity model our symbolic, cultural niche?

Don't mind if I peek (from above)

In order to interpret symbols we have to simultaneously understand whole structures and the individual parts that make them up. Our minds need a full picture, e.g. a word, and the individual components or features, i.e. the letters, without this dual interpretative mode our symbolic capacity would not be possible. This is how we are able to read a word that is composed of individual letters but understand the letters but simultaneously seeing the word as a gestalt, whole ([see here](#) for John Vervaeke's formulation of the feature/gestalt problem of cognition). Letters are only intelligible as a entity if they construct a word and words are only intelligible if they are constructed of letters, likewise for phonemes and spoken words.

This is analogous to a central question of morality that we saw in the hat theft. The collective declaration of an immorality only happened as a result of the man violating the prohibition against hat theft, yet this instance was not explicitly declared in the minds of all those present who came to nonetheless spontaneously explicate it. One way to understand and solve this part-whole paradigm is by focusing on expectation, specifically the implicit structural expectation of harmonious social organization. The hat theft broke the onlookers expectation, or *target state* that did not include what we might call property theft. Theft acted, in Active Inference parlance, as an *error signal* that prompted the corrective action and an explication of this error.

But the story doesn't stop there. What happens if this became a regular occurrences? Not hat theft specifically but maybe people started to aggressively push strangers on the street. At some point society the necessary cascade, or regime of expectations (Constant et al. 2019), would break what is known in economics as social trust (Fukuyama 1996), and the cooperative and productive benefits that accrue following Ricardian specialization.

From an Active Inference point of view, all who witnessed the event had to go along living in a society including innumerable anonymous agents. This problem is solved, however, by establishing 'social types,' or what's known

in group psychology as the phenomenon of [entitativity](#). Norm *violations* are associated with norm *violators*, and violators must quickly correct coarse or be punished. These labels allow us to rapidly communicate with on-lookers such as the police officers who may not have witnessed the event. Most importantly, in terms of personal cognition that minimize surprise sufficiently to allow us to inhabit a world that [involves trust](#) among anonymous and guards against free riders, deviants, or critically, hat thieves.

The establishment of trust through entitizing types determined in response to objectified norms satisfies a necessary condition of our symbolic capacity. Whenever experience symbolic abstraction, whether engaging in language or writing a math equation, we are taking simultaneously an analytic and gestalt view, seeing math symbols as part of an overall paradigm like algebra while interpreting the specific meaning as denoted by the individual symbols. This part-whole paradigm can be resolved by distinguishing between target states and error signals, where the target state is a 'from above' perspective. This allows us the cognitive capacity to dynamically set the context of events and markings in real time.

In the case of morality, i.e. a world of potential hat thieves a situation that was surely present to our distant ancestors during the Pleistocene, draws this out by **extracting the error signal** from the predictive model that underlines self-organization and sentience, this has the effect of exposing the underlying predictive modeling process in the form of symbolic communication and abstract thought prior to the emergence of formal language with its cascade of norms and implicit codes.

In this view, proto-symbolic language takes the form of what linguists call a *performative utterance* which could represent a symbolization of the more primitive *feature placement* (Searle 2010), i.e. a short vocalization used by other animals that are non-symbolic, e.g. the 'waa-bark' and pant-hoots used by chimpanzees or calls by vervet monkey (Boehm 2012; Wilson 2020). This allowed our morality to obtain the bird's eye view that distinguishes it from the social norms practiced by other animals, according to Judith Burkart (Burkart

2018). [Who noted](#) that other primates engage in dyadic, subjective morality that is distinct from humanity's practice of objective morality in our ability to apply it to 'third party' contexts.

Mythical Message Passing

One example of the FEP at work is in hierarchical message passing of the nervous system, where higher cortical areas send predictions to lower levels that contextualize incoming sensory data and send prediction errors in return. This serves as the basis for our perceptual understanding of ourselves and the world, by ensuring we have a sufficiently accurate portrait of the world, where action can be framed, in AIF terms, as bringing the world in accordance to those very predictions.

Canonical cortical microcircuits, schema from (Parr, Pezzulo, and Friston 2022, p. 88)

The idea here is that g represents a predictive model, formulated at the higher cortical layers that, combined with data received from lower level senses, produces corresponding errors. These drive both perception, to produce a more accurate model of the causes of sensory data, action, i.e. by driving motor reflexes and other active states that change the underlying process to match prediction. E.g. sensing that I am hungry (e.g. low glucose levels), seeing available food to eat (both perceptual) and bringing the food to my mouth to fulfill the metabolic prediction associated with being sated (e.g. higher glucose levels).

“god” is predicting

Scaling the above model to our cultural niche, where we all impose intricate and shared normative beliefs is by all conceiving, attempting to conceive, of a shared g function, that models the cultural niche all ‘lower level’ constituents inhabit. Errors that pass through to the upper level, not as a directly observable ‘heavenly’ figure, but as a synthesized top down perspective that allows us to invert, or ‘back-in’ to the causal model.

Essentially, as shown above in the original predictive coding depiction of message passing within cortical microcircuits, higher cortical regions drive perception and action by subtracting predictions from incoming proprioceptive and external sensations (evidence) generating prediction error (*epsilon*), humans experience predictions errors from a synthetic

"above the fray" perspective, i.e. objective or technically transcendent. This may be subtracted from subjective expectations that correspond to expectations that meet narrower, or selfish beliefs.

Taking food sharing as an example, distributing the excess gain from cooperative foraging/hunting practices that vary the likelihood of success based on individual contribution, and set an expectation that gain are distributed to other hunters and those sick and needy (Tomasello et al. 2012), this is subtracted from the subjective expectation that the effective but generally "lucky" hunter distribute his spoils strictly to his own kin. Analogous to the canonical depiction of higher levels of neural hierarchies descending predictions to lower levels and receiving ascending error signals, social expectations now can be said to *technically transcend* individual agents and originate from a synthesized, superordinate hierarchical level.

From Shibboleth to Sky Bias

This is where things get uncomfortable. Math is fine, you might be thinking, but no one wants to talk about social bias. However, in order to understand the transition to symbolic social units it's important to focus in a particular feature of our social groups that we often take for granted, i.e. anonymity. This anonymity can be full blow symbolic, i.e. I recognize someone wearing a uniform as a police officer or soldier in a war, or it can be more impulsive or instinctual. This latter version that takes the form of the psychological phenomenon of in-group bias, is of course more suggestive in an Evolutionary-Development, i.e. ontology (individual development) sort of recapitulates phylogeny (species level evolution).

In-group bias, though used in group psychology, is increasingly applied by biologists to the social aspects of other organisms, for instance see (Masuda and Fu 2015). In active Inference even the individual can be understood as an *optimism bias* (Parr, Pezzulo, and Friston 2022 , p.46), the agent represents a model of the states of the world (niche), but one biased

towards those states that constitute its existence. This amounts to an agent seeking evidence of itself (Hohwy 2016). Extending this to human societies we can understand our transition to symbolic capacity as one that includes an extended in-group.

The claim here is that our ancestors needed to label people, what type of people? In-group violators. Why in-group members rather than out-group people? Isn't the out-group the canonically evil? Well members of the out group are generally dehumanized. This means that while we may acknowledge their capacity to follow rules we generally view their normative capacity and sophistication as significantly below our own. It is not a stretch to extrapolate to our ancestors and imagine them holding all out-group conspecifics in suspicion or contempt. Hence it would not have evoked *surprise* to see someone you already view as beneath you to violate a norm she either did not know or did not care to abide.

This is what the famous ethologist Konrad Lorenz discovered when he noted that:

The dark side of pseudo-speciation is that it makes us consider the members of pseudo-species other than our own as not human, as many primitive tribes are demonstrably doing, in whose language the word for their own particular tribe is synonymous with 'man'.

~ [Konrad Lorenz](#)

Fortunately we have the capacity to symbolically expand our in-groups. Human in-groups are currently effectively boundless. They can include members of your economic class, professional or vocation, compatriot, etc. This is the result of even certain groups that determined by inheritance are essentially as socially constructed as are so many others, clans for instance can be patrilineal or matrilineal, without any cause evident biological basis for the category.

However there is one in-group that remains both extensive and non-symbolic, representing perhaps our most innate in-group bias. This is accent bias, or Shibboleth, our tendency to associate with those with familiar accents. As the name suggest, the bias itself is ancient. [Katherine Kinzler](#) and colleagues suggest it emerges in utero and remains a prevalent form of social injustice throughout our society to this day. From an point of view that understands the self in terms of bias, the impulsive preference to affiliate with those with a familiar accents is a powerful tool of self-extension.

[W]e are not the sum of our received tendencies as a species; rather, we are sophisticated thinkers who can rise above instinct to create beautiful, uniquely human structures of knowledge and behavior. It is high time we took that attitude toward ***speech—the taproot of both bias and the urge to create meaningful social bonds.***

Kinzler, Katherine D (2021, p. 81)

Kinzler’s research suggests the instinctual familiarity bias begins in utero. Emma Cohen and [Mark Moffett](#) follow partly an Evolutionary Development (Evo-Devo) tradition to suggest there is a strong anthropological case that this bias served as a bridge to cultural evolution. Noting accents serve as a reliable and nuanced representation of provenance and suggests the normative pattern one adheres to, (i.e. this is how people *from here* are likely to behave). A way for us to expand group size prior to the capacity for actual symbols. This helped to expand our social learning and what Joseph Henrich calls an autocatalytic culture.

Specifically he notes that environmental predation may have encouraged our ancestors to expand group size, see (Henrich 2016, pp. 300-305), doing so with accents bias would have allowed our ancestors a way to overcome the problems of out-group bias and the practical problems of coordination due to incompatible behavioral norms and social expectations. This bridges the gap between the adhesiveness that binds other extant primate groups, i.e. individual intimacy, to our symbolically bound civilization.

Our social units can therefore be understood in three steps, from a perspective of an average in-group member (A). The first step represents pre-shibboleth social units that, like our primate kindred, included only one's intimates. The second, is the transition to Shibboleth, that allowed an increase in group size without necessarily requiring a symbolic capacity. The third represents the inference of individual social allegiance that rises to free will, or the ability to form one's own beliefs.

Transition to Model (Self) Selection

Step 1) Chimp Sociality: Intimacy Required

$$P(\theta_A) = f[P(Y_B|M_{A+2}) + P(Y_C|M_{A+3}) + P(Y_D|M_{A+4})]$$

Here an Agent A, possess a prior belief that amounts to in-group cohesion. i.e. the number of intimate conspecifics roughly corresponds with those she believes share her generative model. Each Agent (Y) effectively is evidence of a probabilistic model (A + i), which assumes a common Markov blanket, or view of the generative process, i.e. cultural niche as Agent A. Moffett notes that this requires that roughly each individual agent be intimate with all others, though she may have intimates that are no longer part of her in-group due, i.e. children find mates in other social units, she acknowledges now that these individuals are no longer considered an in-group.

Regardless, all members of the in-group must not be foreign to any member which would lead to conflict and threaten the integrity. Note this is consistent with the use of 'in-group' preferences or bias by (Masuda and Fu 2015) to better understand the dynamical constraints of social units, and generally consistent with the self as optimism bias per Active Inference.

Written in General Form:

$$P(\theta_A|M_{A+i}) = \tilde{g}[P(Y_X|M_{A+i})]$$

g = prediction of conspecifics

i = total compatriots a given Agent can cognitively compute as in-group

Step 2) Anonymous Shibboleth In-group

Agent A now expects those with certain accents to possess the same in-group model. Note, one argument in favor of accent-bias as an evolutionary tool to expand group size and cooperative potential is its ability to effectively scale based on a certain proximity to one's own, i.e. if I am from Rhode Island, I may trust someone more from my home town than Boston, but trust Boston more than a Canadian, etc. The distinction is context specific and likely favors the more proximal in-group member, all else equal. However I turn this into a binary model of in-group anonymity. This is important for simplicity, or 'parsimony' that represents the need, at any given time, to distinguish between friend and foe, or otherwise select between potential alternative collaborators.

$$P(\theta_{t-1}^A) = \tilde{g}^B [P(Y^B | M^{shib} + \epsilon^B)]$$

This states now, that our protagonist agent A, now sees qualifying conspecifics as part of a model signified with shibboleth.

Step 2 a) Challenge to Shibboleth: Initial Posterior

In this transitional period, observations of behavior that defined the in-group behavioral expectations set by Shibboleth would challenge 'model surprise', i.e. the marginal likelihood ($P(y)$) of seeing a violator, this contrasts with the other notion, known as 'Bayesian Surprise' that is the update from a prior to a posterior belief. In the typical circumstance, deviations would simply trigger a response, e.g. a collective response to an over-aggressive alpha.

However, in the context of social anonymity, where accents afford only what we might call *synthetic intimacy*, agents are unknown to one another, a norm violation would threaten the very integrity of the social unit. Although this

weakens shibboleth as perhaps the noisy signal it remains today of behavioral expectations, it need not represent the dissolution of the social unit it originally established. Introducing an *objective error*, a view that behavioral deviations are not just in relation to dyadic arrangements, but exist within a neutral third party context, offers the requisite immediate cognitive response.

I represent this surprise, or error as a prediction error that reaches a threshold. Using Pseudo if then statement to understand how a critical switch that involved, in this theory, a transition from Bayesian surprise to marginal likelihood.

If):

$$\epsilon_{t0}^B \geq S$$

Then):

$$P(\theta_{t0}^A | Y^B) = \tilde{g}^B [P(Y^B | M^{dev})]$$

Else):

$$P(\theta_{t0}^A | Y^B) = \tilde{g}^B [P(Y^B | M^{shib})]$$

This implies now that the agent possess a self-awareness, an extension of self-awareness that follows the recognition of internal, (felt) subjective emotional states in others, now, recognizing that agents not only possess internal states but construct a model that depends on compliance to or deviation from the inferred predictions or expectations of a synthesized superordinate layer of the social hierarchy. i.e. the cultural niche.

Step 3) Posterior: The trick of the hat thief

Following on from the *then* condition above, i.e. where an agent observes a deviation and responds, as Mark Solms notes of thought, to thwart the lower

level affective response:

[A]ffects make demands upon the mind, and [...] cognition performs the work so demanded. To be more precise, conscious cognition performs the work; for once it has been performed, and confidence in the (prioritised) belief that had become uncertain has been restored, the generative model resumes its automatic mode of operation, below the threshold of awareness. [...] This is the whole point of consciousness in cognition. You arrive at a situation in which you aren't sure what to do. Consciousness comes to the rescue: you feel your way through the scenario, noting the voluntary actions that work for you. ~ (Solms 2022, p. 220]

To return to our bizarro hat caper - picture now the crowd without the impulse to produce labels. Observing the particular instance of hat theft, to go back inhabit their cultural niche the bystanders would have to clutch tightly onto their own hats, no doubt encouraging some to engage in more hat theft, and perhaps other personal possessions as well. In other words, a sense of fear, rage, etc. would persist without the utility of the label, feelings that would be tethered to the now less certain boundaries of the cultural niche.

Where as norms in an environment of intimacy emerged from what we can view as a political exchange of power dynamics, i.e. between alphas and betas, between individuals and coalitions with each pursuing their own expectations, in an anonymous social unit require a more immediate and explicit response.

$$P(\theta_{i1}^A | \epsilon^{obj}) = \tilde{g}^{obj}(\tilde{g}^{n+i}(\theta_{[c,d]}))$$

By explicating the error, we thus synthesized, what some call *higher order* consciousness, the ability to transcend intersubjectivity, to achieve [transjectivity](#), i.e. see the world from a higher perspective, but viewing this perspective in relation to another agent's self-beliefs. Given that

this occurs for in-group conspecifics, the outer objective g became a fixture for all in our social unit, coming to serve as evidence that stood in relation to other in-group suggestions, like intimacy and shibboleth and later extending to other symbolic insignia.

The prediction error now becomes foregrounded as we both minimize the surprise with an abstract label, and begin to utilize it as a signal of our own allegiance. This aligns with the prevalence of gossiping in typical communication, we spend a great deal of time letting others know how we feel about norm violations and violators, see ([Dunbar 2004](#)).

Moral Agency: The Original Metaverse

In active inference, the need to form a coherent model of one's world is fulfilled by establishing an approximation of the hidden causes of sensory data, known as minimizing variational free energy. Cognitive systems are unique specifically because of this approximation, giving way to effectively to the self as type of prediction error, where identity emerges as a statical bias that includes one's self, being just wrong enough about the actual world to ensure that one doing the modeling persists in it. Given this, introducing moral objectivity as an extraction of prediction error effectively transitions us to new form of cognition. One that involves an agent that inhabits a higher, virtual world of its own selection.

Our world from one where an agent is seen as responding to the environment to one in which it selects its own world. In the simple case of the deviant and compliant, their model of the world either accepts the expectations of the superordinate social unit or defines them. The novelty here lies in something like *active deviation*, where we expect an agent possesses predictions that follow the Bayesian beliefs of the shared generative model of the cultural unit, but instead opts for a narrower one.

This active model toggling, or divergence between the cultural unit and a deviant agent is analogous to the KL divergence between the variational free

energy F that acts, statistically, as an attempt to model the true distribution of the data y .

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Taken from (Parr, Pezzulo, and Friston 2022, p. 29)

$$P(\theta^A) = g[\delta(Y|M) \leq D_{KL}] , \text{ Where } D_{KL} = 0$$

Note that the very act of modeling, of approximating oneself, introduces a less than perfect fit, i.e. we may literally exist because we are not perfect (models) of the environment. More formally:

One perspective on the difference between cognitive and noncognitive systems is that the latter always have a zero KL-Divergence, while cognitive systems must go through the (perceptual) process of minimizing this term before their actions are guaranteed to minimize surprise. (Parr, Pezzulo, and Friston 2022, p. 51)

Note also the view of Michael Levin and Daniel Dennett, that cognition is not the privilege of complex organisms, but rather exists [all the way down](#), meaning at all scales of life. Hence this divergence is perhaps a defining feature of sentience.

Given this we can understand humanity's transition to a technically transcendent viewpoint, or the perspective that underwrites our cultural niche and capacity to interpret and produce symbolic materials and thoughts, as the belief in an extensive social unit and conditioned on prediction errors, that give way to the inference that agents can approximate, or bias their beliefs to align with the cultural niche or depart from it.

During this transitional period, Agent A is attempting to reconcile the deviant agent's surprising behavior, noticing a large divergence between the "actual" model of the world that represents its prior belief, and the agent's ability to disregard the norms implied by this belief. Hence the distinction between the virtual posterior and the actual model the deviant inhabits.

$$F[Q_v, \epsilon^{obj}] \geq D_{KL} Q_v(x_v) || P(x_A | \epsilon^{obj}, M_A) - \ln(P(\epsilon^{obj} | M_A))$$

This is represented by the subscript v attached to Q, the approximate posterior distribution that cognitive agents possess, ensuring they have the complexity-favorable ability to diverge from the environment. The virtualization of this term simply denotes the newfound capacity to serve a narrower self, but even this narrowed selection process affords the deviant and potentially anonymous agent the capacity to at least toggle between hierarchical predictive levels.

Possessing a virtualized model of a natural world, however, transitions into the belief that the world itself is as *literal* as it was prior to this act of model selection (i.e. moral agency or free will perhaps). This generalizes post-modern semiotician, Jean Baudrillard critique of the increasing disconnectedness of human society from nature, recognizing that the

introduction of symbolic consciousness involves at least a minimal degree of a virtual, generative model and process.

$$W_A \Rightarrow M_A : M_V \Rightarrow W_V$$

Where W_A represents the actual world and W_V represents the virtual world. The arrow depicts the transition of how we infer causality, initially as the world being the prime mover of the model (while allowing for action to update the world, etc.), whereas the transition suggests an agent virtually models itself in accordance to a bespoke, virtual world.

Conclusion

Given the claim is explicating moral norms as a central feature of the human experience, it's worth evaluating what this implies about morality itself. Is morality always explicating or are their implicit, innate forms of moral behavior? Taking ancient text of morality and belief, the baghad Gita, captures the inherent connection of the objective moral impulse and it's connection between explicit and implicit consciousness experience. The protagonist, Arjuna, is on route to engage in a violent battle, where he becomes concerned that some of his enemies are his own kindred. The god Vishnu appears to assert that it is his duty (Dharma) to nonetheless engage in battle.

Viewing morality as a prediction error, or more intuitively, as a failure of behavioral expectations, frame's Arjuna's dilemma as the break-point in his otherwise dharmic flow, i.e. the expectation of harmony within one's 'being' is the dao, precisely (i believe) from that break-point, we interrupt the code of existence. This is also the crux of existentialism Heidegger, that humans are the one animals without an 'essence.' this ability to question our behavior is tied to our symbolic capacity, that first and foremost influences our self-evidentiary epistemic foraging.

Framing this using additional formalism would help expand this to other social, economic, and civil institutions, i.e. explicating the tensor networks

that formalize control as switching between Markov blankets, is beyond the scope but a logical next step, as is producing a simulation that implements the above equations.